

RESORCINOL, ACONITEIN AND TRICARBALLYLEIN AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS IN ARGENTOMETRIC TITRATIONS

BY RAM CHARAN MEHROTRA

In a comparative study of the behaviour of resorcinol aconitein and tricarballylein as adsorption indicators in argentometric titrations, it has been observed that whereas the latter is a very suitable indicator for the purpose, the former does not develop any distinct colour on being adsorbed on the silver halide bodies. The observed difference has been explained in a simple manner and casually confirms the structure assigned to the aconitein by the previous workers. As a result of the investigation, a very sensitive indicator for the titration of halide and thiocyanate ions against silver ions has been described.

In a recent communication from these laboratories (Mehrotra, this *Journal*, 1948, 28, 523, it has been shown that whereas dyes derived from succinic acid-resorcinol succinein and itacone in serve as very suitable indicators for the titrations of halide ions against silver ions, the corresponding dyes from maleic acid-resorcinol malein and citraconein are not at all suitable for the purpose. The difference in the behaviour of the two classes of dyes has been explained on the basis of restricted rotation due to a double bond in the maleic acid derivatives. It was considered of interest to extend the study to the comparative behaviour of resorcinol aconitein and tricarballylein. Resorcinol aconitein and tricarballylein have the structure (I) and (II) shown below :

Resorcinol aconitein

Resorcinol tricarballylein.

Aconitic anhydride could theoretically have either of the structures (III) or (IV), but the former is the more stable of the two because the interposition of a double bond between the two carbon atoms brings the two carboxylic groups so near to each other that the anhydride formation between them takes place with the greatest ease (Beasley, Ingold and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1080 ; Ingold and Thorpe, *ibid.*, 1919, 115, 320 ; Kon, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 810 ; Dhar and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 253).

(III)

(IV)

Dikshit and Tewari (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2511) have arrived at similar conclusions from a study of the dyes derived from the two acids. It is of interest to observe that the comparative behaviour of the resorcinol dyes of these acids as adsorption indicators is in agreement with the structures proposed above. Like the derivatives of maleic acid-resorcinol malein and citraconein, resorcinol aconitein also is not a suitable adsorption indicator for the argentometric titrations, whereas the corresponding succinic acid derivative, resorcinol tricarballylein marks the end-points very sharply in the titrations of halide ions against silver ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dyes, resorcinol aconitein and tricarballylein, were prepared according to the method described by Dikshit and Tewari (*loc. cit.*). 0.1% Solutions of the dyes were prepared in alcohol and these solutions (generally one drop for each 5 c.c. of the halide solution to be titrated) were employed as adsorption indicators throughout the following investigations.

Titration of Chloride Ions against Silver Ions.—When a chloride solution (about $N/10$) is taken in a beaker and a drop of resorcinol tricarballylein is added to it, the solution shows a brilliant green fluorescence. As the silver nitrate solution (about $N/10$) is gradually added to it, the solution becomes yellow. Coagulation of the silver chloride begins quite early and the particles take up a slight pinkish shade. Just at the equivalent point, with half a drop of the silver nitrate solution, the precipitate as well as the supernatant suspension takes up a very bright pink shade. The colour on the particles becomes much lighter when a few drops of acetic acid ($N/10$) is added to the washed pink precipitate; the colour on the particles disappears also with the addition of ammonia to the precipitate with the appearance of a bright green fluorescence in the supernatant solution. When the titrating solutions have a concentration of about ($N/100$), the colour change (pinkish yellow to bright pink) occurs in the suspension phase. The colour change is quite reversible; even in the more concentrated solutions, though the colour change occurs on the coagulated particles, yet the colour change is so reversible that the titration can be carried out accurately even in the opposite direction.

However, when resorcinol aconitein is used as indicator instead of the tricarballylein, the pink colour developed on the particles on the adsorption of the dye at the equivalent point is much lighter in shade and the end-point is not at all sharp. The chloride solution with a few drops of the indicator added to it has a light yellow colour and takes up a light orange colour as a little silver nitrate solution is run in. The co-

agulation of the precipitate begins quite early, but the particles remain almost colorless and become light pink at the equivalent point (about 0.6% excess of silver nitrate is required).

Titration of Thiocyanate Ions against Silver Ions.—When the solutions having a concentration of about ($N/10$) are titrated using resorcinol tricarbalylein as adsorption indicator, the coagulation of the precipitate begins quite early, but just at the equivalent point the bright yellow colour of the suspension is discharged with a simultaneous development of a bright pink colour on the particles of the coagulated precipitate which remains white in shade before the end-point. The above colour change, though occurring on the particles of the coagulated precipitate, is very sharp and quite reversible. In the case the solutions are dilute (about $N/200$), a very sensitive colour change from yellow to pink occurs in the apparently homogeneous suspension phase.

However, as in the case of the chloride, the end-point is not so sharp and the pink shade developed on the particles is much lighter when resorcinol aconitein is used as indicator instead of the tricarbalylein.

Titration of the Bromide Ions against Silver Ions.—Using resorcinol tricarbalylein as adsorption indicator, a very sharp colour change from yellow to bright pink occurs at the equivalent point. The colour change occurs on the particles of the coagulated precipitate in the case of the concentrated solutions, but in the suspension phase, when the titrating solutions are dilute. The titration with sharp end-points is possible when the solutions have a dilution up to about $N/500$. The colour change is quite reversible and the titration is possible in the reverse order with the colour change occurring in the opposite manner.

The end-point are not at all sharp using resorcinol aconitein as adsorption indicator. The colour developed on the particles on the adsorption of the dye is very light and quite indistinct.

Titration of Iodide Ions against Silver Ions.—When a iodide solution is titrated against silver nitrate solution using resorcinol tricarbalylein as adsorption indicator, a very sharp and quite reversible colour change from yellow to bright pink occurs. When the solutions are relatively concentrated, then the coagulation of the precipitate occurs almost simultaneously with the adsorption of the dye at the equivalent point. In the case of dilute solutions, the suspension retains a bright green fluorescence up to the end-point and at the equivalent point, half a drop of the silver nitrate solution inhibits the fluorescence and makes the suspension pink. The end-point is quite sharp even when the titrating solutions are as dilute as $N/1000$.

In the case when resorcinol aconitein is used as adsorption indicator, similar colour changes take place and the end-point is easily detectable, but the colour developed on the particles or in the suspension phase is much lighter. Solutions can be titrated upto a dilution of $N/500$.

The following table records a few of the experimental results obtained using resorcinol tricarbalylein as adsorption indicator :

TABLE I

Conc. of halide soln. (5 c.c. taken).	Drops of Indicator.	AgNO ₃ soln.	Transition of colour.	Remarks.
N/10-KCl	2	4.99 to 5.01 c.c., of N/10	Yellow susp. →pink ppt.	The end-point is very sharp and quite reversible. The titration is possible in the opposite direction.
N/100-KCl	2	5 to 5.02 c.c. of N/100	Pink-yellow susp. →pink susp.	"
N/10-KCNS	2	5.00 c.c. of N/10	White ppt. →pink ppt.	The coagulation of the ppt. occurs very early. The colour change is very sharp and reversible.
N/200-KCNS	2	5.02 c.c. of N/200	Yellow susp. →pink susp.	The silver thiocyanate does not coagulate at all. The end-point is very sharp and reversible.
N/500-KBr	1	5.02 to 5.03 c.c. of N/500	Yellow susp. →pink susp.	End-point is quite sharp and occurs in the apparently homogeneous phase. The titration is possible in opposite direction.
N/100-KI	2	5 to 5.02 c.c. of N/10	Yellow susp. →pink ppt.	The coagulation occurs just at the end-point with the transference of the yellow colour of the suspension to a bright pink colour on ppt.
N/1000-KI	1	5 to 5.02 c.c. of N/1000	Greenish yellow susp. →pinkish yellow susp.	The solution has a bright green fluorescence right up to the end-point. Just at the end-point, the fluorescence ceases, being replaced by a pinkish tinge.

DISCUSSION

As has been shown in the earlier communication (*loc. cit.*), the deformability of the electronic orbits and consequently the development of colour on adsorption is much inhibited when a double bond is present at an active spot in the dye molecule. The reasoning put forward by Thorpe and co-workers in favour of the structure (III) as the one representing the aconitein can be applied for explaining the cause of a much lesser development of colour in the case of the aconitein than in the case of tricarbalylein. The presence of the double bond make the anhydride formation much easier in the case of the maleic acid derivatives and hence the opening of this anhydride ring which requires a greater force and strain in the case of maleic acid derivatives than in the corresponding succinic acid derivatives. This lessening of the ease with which the anhydride ring can be opened will have an effect in inhibiting the tautomeric change producing the quinonoid structure, as it requires the opening of the said ring and hence the colour will be much less pronounced in the case of maleic acid derivatives than in the corresponding succinic acid derivatives. The observed difference in the behaviour of the resorcinol aconitein and tricarbalylein is thus simply explained.

The author wishes to thank Dr. J. D. Tewari for his kind help in the preparation of the indicator dyes.